

STRENGTHENING MARKETPLACE-BASED BRANDING AND MARKETING THROUGH A DIGITAL MENTORING APPROACH TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF JAN ENDOLS COOKIES MSMEs IN SIDOARJO REGENCY

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Abstract

The Jan Endols Dry Cake MSME in Sidoarjo Regency is a custom-made culinary business still managed conventionally, particularly in operational management and marketing strategies. This situation limits business efficiency and market reach, making digitalization a strategic necessity to increase competitiveness. This community service activity aims to strengthen the management and marketing of MSMEs through digital-based mentoring. The mentoring is carried out in a participatory and implementative manner through stages of observation, problem identification, training, and monitoring and evaluation tailored to the needs and capacities of business actors. The mentoring focuses on implementing simple digital financial records, managing orders and production processes, and utilizing social media and marketplaces as marketing tools. The activity results show increased operational efficiency, expanded marketing reach, and an increased understanding and ability of MSMEs in utilizing digital technology. These findings confirm that digital mentoring has significant potential to support the strengthening of management, marketing, and sustainability of culinary MSMEs at the local level, while also serving as a mentoring model for other MSMEs with similar characteristics.

Keywords: *MSME Assistance, Business Digitalization, Branding, Digital Marketing*

A. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a strategic role in the Indonesian economy, particularly in job creation, poverty reduction, and strengthening local economies in both rural and urban areas (Abas et al., 2023; Tambunan, 2019). MSMEs also contribute to improving community welfare and driving inclusive economic growth. The development of digital technology has brought significant changes to business management, including aspects of production, marketing, and financial record-keeping. Business digitalization, particularly in digital marketing, is a strategic necessity for MSMEs to compete in the era of globalization and the transformation of Industry 4.0 (OECD, 2021). However, low digital literacy and limited human resources remain major obstacles for MSMEs in optimally adopting digital technology (Rahayu & Day, 2017).

Jan Endols Cookies, a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) located in Sidoarjo Regency, is a custom-made culinary business established in 2023. It produces various types of cookies and traditional cakes, such as nastar (pineapple cake), putri salju (snow white cookies), and lidah kucing (cat's tongue), which are in high demand during certain times such as religious holidays and year-end celebrations. While the custom-made production system maintains product quality, the business is still managed conventionally, particularly in financial record-keeping, operational management, and marketing, which is still limited to the use of personal social media.

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The challenges faced by Jan Endols Dry Cakes reflect the general situation of many micro-SMEs in Indonesia, where digitalization of management and marketing has not been optimally utilized. Various studies have shown that digital marketing development assistance can help MSMEs expand their market reach, increase customer engagement, and strengthen product identity through the use of social media and marketplaces (Amiroh et al., 2022; Fitriani et al., 2025). From a marketing perspective, digital marketing plays a crucial role in business strategy because it overcomes the limitations of conventional marketing, expands consumer engagement, and strengthens brand identity through digital content and communications (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Furthermore, digital-based mentoring for MSMEs aligns with the sustainable development agenda, particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure). Based on these conditions, this community service activity was designed to implement a digital mentoring strategy to strengthen the management, branding, and marketing of Jan Endols Dry Cake MSMEs in Sidoarjo Regency. The mentoring focused on implementing simple digital financial record keeping, managing business operations, and optimizing marketing and branding awareness through participation in events, social media, and marketplaces in an applicable and implementable manner, to increase business competitiveness and sustainability.

B. METHOD

Mentoring activities were implemented using a descriptive qualitative approach with participatory methods, emphasizing direct collaboration between the mentoring team and MSME owners. This approach was chosen to ensure that the mentoring strategy implemented was aligned with field conditions, actual needs, and the characteristics of the partner businesses (Amiroh et al., 2022; Fitriani et al., 2025). The participatory method allows MSMEs to be actively involved in every stage of the activity, so that the resulting solutions are applicable and easy to implement in daily business activities. The main stages of mentoring include: Mentoring is carried out using a descriptive qualitative approach and participatory methods, emphasizing direct collaboration between the mentoring team and MSME owners. This approach is chosen so that the strategies implemented are in accordance with field needs and business characteristics. The main stages of mentoring include:

1. Initial Survey & Observation

The initial phase involved collecting business profile data, product samples of dry cakes and wet cakes, and directly observing the production process carried out by the Jan Endols Dry Cakes MSME. These observations aimed to obtain a picture of the business's initial conditions as a basis for formulating a mentoring program.

2. Problem Identification and Program Development

Based on the survey and observation results, key challenges faced by MSMEs were identified, including limited human resources, suboptimal digital marketing, and manual financial record-keeping. The support team, along with MSME owners, developed a development and mentoring program tailored to the needs and capacity of Jan Endols' MSME partners.

3. Digitalization Technical Training and Mentoring

This stage includes training and technical assistance covering social media management, such as Instagram, digital catalog development, the use of simple marketplaces as marketing tools, and the implementation of simple digital financial record-keeping. The assistance is provided directly in practice so that MSMEs can understand and apply the material independently (Rahayu & Day, 2017).

4. Monitoring and Evaluation of Implementation

Monitoring and evaluation are conducted through regular discussion sessions between the support team and MSMEs to assess the progress of the solutions implemented. Evaluations focus on changes in business management, digital marketing utilization, and MSMEs' understanding of the use of digital technology in their operations.

This mentoring approach and stages are consistent with the community service methodology for MSMEs, which has been proven to improve digital literacy and business operational performance (Fitriani et al., 2025).

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C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of MSME Mentoring

Mentoring activities for the Jan Endols Dry Cake MSME in Sidoarjo Regency were carried out through specifically designed stages. The mentoring method was direct and participatory, ensuring that MSMEs were actively involved in every step of implementing the solutions. This approach allowed for mentoring strategies to be tailored to the actual business conditions and needs of MSMEs (Amiroh et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Initial discussion on mentoring for Jan Endols Dry Cake MSMEs

2. Implementation of Digitalization in Financial Recording and Operational Management

One of the main outcomes of the mentoring activity was the implementation of simple digital financial record keeping at the Jan Endols Dry Cakes MSME. Prior to the mentoring, financial record keeping was done manually and unstructured, making it difficult for MSMEs to monitor cash flow and business performance. Through the mentoring, MSMEs began implementing digital financial record keeping that is more organized and easier to understand. This aligns with Rahayu & Day (2017), who stated that adopting digital technology can improve MSME operational efficiency.

Figure 2. Digital financial recording of MSMEs

LAPORAN KEUANGAN JAN ENDOLS																				01 Desember 2021							
ITEM	KUE KERING										KUE BASAH									TOTAL							
	Lidah Kuning Vanila	Lidah Kuning Kacang	Kue Kacang	Putri Saja	Rastar	Choco chips	Sempol Kacang	Sempol Mentar	Janda Genit	Chai Kacao So	Mini Pizza	Roti Sosis	Risol Rogur	Risol Mayo	Gabin Tape	Sau Fla Vanilla	Donat Mini	Mini Cake	Onde-onde Kacang		Pie Bush	Pie Borek	Fudge Breyers	Brownies Lumut	Bolu Susu	Bolu Susu	
Bahan																											
Tapung	Rp 3,600		Rp 6,000	Rp 6,000																		Rp 8,400					Rp 24,000
Margarin	Rp 6,000				Rp 10,000																	Rp 12,500					Rp 28,500
Butter/sab	Rp 4,000				Rp 4,000																						Rp 8,000
Gula	Rp 3,600		Rp 3,600	Rp 1,800																		Rp 3,670					Rp 12,670
Telur	Rp 4,000		Rp 4,000	Rp 4,000																		Rp 3,600					Rp 15,600
Minyak			Rp 10,000																			Rp 2,200					Rp 12,200
Mentana					Rp 800																						Rp 800
Susu Bubuk					Rp 2,000																						Rp 2,000
Coaklet Bubuk																						Rp 8,750					Rp 8,750
Dark Colort																						Rp 12,000					Rp 12,000
Kacang			Rp 10,000																								Rp 10,000
Essence Vanilla	Rp 2,000																										Rp 2,000
Baking Powder	Rp 300																										Rp 300
Gula halus					Rp 2,500																						Rp 2,500
Total Biaya Bahan	Rp 23,700		Rp 33,600	Rp 31,100																		Rp 51,330					Rp 137,230
Packaging																											
Toples	Rp 12,000		Rp 9,000	Rp 9,000																							Rp 30,000
Stiker	Rp 2,000		Rp 1,500	Rp 1,500																							Rp 5,000
Mata-wapornisasi																						Rp 4,000					Rp 4,000
Total biaya packaging	Rp 14,000		Rp 10,500	Rp 10,500																		Rp 4,900					Rp 39,800
Energi																											
Listrik & Air	Rp 2,500		Rp 2,500	Rp 2,500																							Rp 10,000
Gas	Rp 750																										Rp 750
Total Biaya Energi	Rp 2,500		Rp 2,500	Rp 2,500																		Rp 3,250					Rp 11,500
TOTAL BIAYA PRODUKSI	Rp 40,200		Rp 47,350	Rp 44,100																		Rp 59,330					Rp 188,530
Jumlah Terjual	4	3	3	3																		48					
Harga Jual	Rp 20,000	Rp 22,000	Rp 30,000	Rp 30,000	Rp 35,000	Rp 30,000	Rp 25,000	Rp 25,000	Rp 28,000	Rp 30,000	Rp 2,500	Rp 5,000	Rp 7,000	Rp 2,500													
TOTAL PENUALAN	Rp 80,000	Rp 66,000	Rp 90,000	Rp 90,000	Rp 105,000	Rp 90,000	Rp 75,000	Rp 75,000	Rp 84,000	Rp 90,000	Rp 6,250	Rp 12,500	Rp 17,500	Rp 6,250													
LABA	Rp 39,800	Rp 29,650	Rp 42,650	Rp 45,900	Rp 60,000	Rp 45,900																					

3. Strengthening Digital Marketing through Rebranding and Social Media Optimization

One of the key outcomes of the mentoring activity was the rebranding and optimization of the Jan Endols Dry Cake MSME's social media accounts. The mentoring team updated the appearance of the @jan.endols Instagram account by improving the content design to make it more attractive and professional. This rebranding included rearranging the feed layout and using consistent colors and visual elements. to display the product catalog . The results of the rebranding activity showed increased engagement and audience reach on MSME social media accounts. Business owners began to understand the importance of visual consistency and audience engagement in building a stronger and more professional brand image on digital media. This

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finding aligns with Kotler and Keller (2016), who emphasized that consistent brand identity and visual communication play a crucial role in building consumer trust.

Figure 3. Rebranding of Jan Endols' Instagram account

4. Marketplace Development as a Marketing Tool

In addition to optimizing social media, mentoring also focused on developing marketing through marketplaces. The Jan Endols Kue Kering MSME was assisted in creating and managing accounts on the Shopee and TikTok platforms as interactive promotional and sales tools. In addition to contributing to increased sales, utilizing marketplaces also expanded customer reach beyond Sidoarjo Regency. This supports the findings of Rahayu and Day (2017) that adopting digital platforms can help MSMEs reach a wider market at a relatively efficient

Figure 4. Jan Endols' Shopee and TikTok accounts

5. Increase Business Visibility through Banner, Flyer, and Google Maps Design

Assistance efforts are also being made to increase local business visibility by creating new banner and flyer designs for display at business locations. Furthermore, the support team is helping optimize MSMEs' presence on Google Maps by managing customer reviews. This step aims to make it easier for potential customers to find business locations quickly and accurately and to increase trust through positive consumer reviews. The results of this activity showed an increase in the number of local customers, especially those who discovered the business through digital searches. Optimizing the visual identity and local digital presence has been shown to contribute to increased trust and business appeal.

Figure 5. Jan Endols' New Banner and Flyer Design

Figure 6. Location Point and Customer Reviews of Jan Endols on Google Maps

6. Promotion Program Implementation

As part of strengthening their marketing strategy, the mentoring team assisted MSMEs in implementing the "Everything for Rp2,500" promotional program for wet cakes in local event "Car Free Day". This promotional program was designed to attract new customers, increase brand awareness, and accelerate product turnover, all with the aim of increasing consumer purchasing interest. Implementation results showed that the structured promotional strategy had a positive impact on increasing sales and consumer awareness and loyalty.

Figure 7. Jan Endols Promotion Program in Local Event

D. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Conclusion

The digital mentoring program provided to Jan Endols Dry Cakes MSMEs demonstrated that digitalization of management, marketing, and branding can significantly improve business performance. Through systematic mentoring stages, including initial surveys and observations, problem identification and program development, technical training and digital mentoring, and implementation monitoring and evaluation, MSMEs were able to identify business issues in a more structured manner and find solutions tailored to field conditions.

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The results of the activity show that implementing digitalization in marketing and financial recording can improve operational efficiency and expand market reach. Utilizing social media and marketplaces as promotional and sales tools helps MSMEs run their businesses in a more integrated and adaptive manner to technological developments. Furthermore, innovative and consistent promotional strategies through digital media have been proven to contribute to increased sales and customer loyalty. Overall, this mentoring activity emphasized that the sustainability of local MSMEs requires a synergy between digital innovation, adaptive marketing strategies, and human resource empowerment. Jan Endols Kue Kering MSME serves as an example of how implementing appropriate business and technology strategies can increase business competitiveness, strengthen MSMEs' confidence in utilizing technology, and drive sustainable regional economic growth.

2. Recommendation

Based on the results of the community service activities that have been carried out, several recommendations that can be given include:

- a. MSMEs are advised to maintain consistency in implementing digital financial records and digital marketing management so that the impact of the mentoring can be sustainable.
- b. Digital marketing content development needs to be carried out continuously by utilizing social media insight data to increase promotional effectiveness.
- c. Similar mentoring programs need to be continued and expanded, both through collaboration with universities and other stakeholders, to support the acceleration of MSME digital transformation.
- d. Further research and community service are recommended to examine the long-term impact of digital mentoring on the performance and sustainability of MSMEs.

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